

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Visualization of the output of Sound Event Detection algorithms in Freesound

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to birds.

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Abstract

This thesis presents a postprocessing and visualization pipeline for the output of sound event detection (SED) models, with a specific focus on the FSD-SINet model and its integration within the Freesound platform.

The first part of the work addresses the refinement of SED outputs by proposing several postprocessing methodologies to improve the quality and usability of detection results. These include proposals to obtain adaptive parameters per class for the postprocessing pipeline, tag recommendation strategies applied to SED systems, hierarchical filtering based on the dataset vocabulary, and exploration of future optimization techniques.

The second part of the project focuses on the design and evaluation of visualization approaches to display SED outputs in a user-friendly manner directly within Freesound. Several interface displays are proposed and analyzed in terms of clarity, space efficiency and user interaction. A user satisfaction experiment is designed to evaluate these approaches based on real user's feedback.

By connecting these two parts, this work aims to make crucial steps in making SED technology more accessible to the broader Freesound community, while contributing to the platform's development and user experience improvement.

Keywords: Sound Event Detection; Postprocessing; User interface

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Freesound is a collaborative online platform that hosts a vast collection of sounds ranging from audio snippets and musical samples to all kinds of recordings. With millions of downloads and an active community of users and moderators, Freesound serves as a crucial resource for artists, researchers, sound designers, and sound enthusiasts across many fields. Its value lies not only in the diversity and volume of its content but also in the community-generated metadata (tags, descriptions and comments) that enrich each audio file.

In addition, Freesound features an audio analysis pipeline composed of several analyzers that extract various properties from the uploaded sounds. These properties range from low-level audio descriptors to the outputs of state-of-the-art machine learning models for Sound Event Detection (SED). However, despite the relevance of this high-level information, it is currently not displayed on the Freesound website. Although this may seem like an unconventional focus for a master's thesis, this project aims to take the final steps in making this data useful, accessible, and meaningful to the broader Freesound community, a frequently overlooked but essential step for translating research into real-world impact.

Finally, this work takes place during Freesound's 20th anniversary and coincides

with my personal experience as a Software Engineering Intern at the platform. During this time, I have contributed to resolving user and developer-reported issues and participated in the design and implementation of new features supporting the creation of collaborative sound collections.

1.2 Objectives

This thesis aims to enhance the use of Sound Event Detection (SED) outputs by improving postprocessing techniques and designing intuitive visualizations, all integrated into the Freesound platform. Building on the FSD-SINet model, the first objective is to improve the postprocessing of detection outputs through methods such as adaptive thresholding, tag recommendation strategies, and ontology-based filtering.

The second objective is to design and evaluate visualization approaches that make SED results more interpretable and useful for Freesound users. This involves creating multiple display proposals, incorporating user interaction features, and selecting the most effective designs based on a user satisfaction study.

Together, these objectives aim to bridge the gap between machine learning outputs and practical user applications.

1.3 Structure of the Report

The rest of this thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides some basic definitions and current state-of-the-art datasets, benchmarks and postprocessing methods for SED systems, and current user interfaces for sound annotations. In Chapter 3, the proposed postprocessing approaches are detailed as well as the different visualization prototypes and user satisfaction experiment design.

Chapter 4 will contains the results of this study with a reduced number of respondents. In the final chapter, the obtained results are discussed and some insights are provided on the work of this project, as well as the future steps and work to be

carried out for this feature to be fully integrated into Freesound.

Chapter 2

State of the art

This chapter reviews the fundamentals and latest advancements in the literature of this work. Given that the scope of this thesis involves two main topics, post-processing for the outputs of sound event detection algorithms, and its visualization and user interface design, they are treated separately.

2.1 Foundations of Sound Event detection

2.1.1 Problem definitions

Sound event detection (SED) is a rapidly evolving subfield of computational analysis of sound scenes that involves the automatic identification and classification of acoustic events in real world audio recordings. Sound event detection aims not only at recognizing the presence of sound events; sounds produced by a single source (dog barking, car passing by...) but also at localizing these events in the temporal domain. This subsection introduces the core problem formulations involved in the process of sound event detection: audio tagging, event detection and segmentation and the distinction between monophonic vs polyphonic detections.

Audio Tagging vs Event Detection.

Sound scene analysis research is fundamentally divided into audio tagging and event detection. On the one hand, audio tagging refers to the task of assigning one or more labels to an audio clip to determine which classes are present, without specifying its temporal information. This is usually treated as a multi-label classification task (cita al llibre!) and is appropriate for weakly labeled datasets where annotations are provided for each audio clip. Common benchmarks such as Audioset [1] and FSD50K [2] provide large-scale data for this goal. On the other hand, sound event detection requires, not only identifying which classes are present in an audio clip but also delimiting its time boundaries i.e. predicting their onsets and offset along the temporal domain for each event. This requirement transforms the problem into a localization task evaluated using event-based metrics such as F1-Score and error rate (ER) [3]. Therefore, event detection is a more demanding and complex task than tagging, especially when dealing with real-world auditory scenes, where multiple events tend to overlap.

Monophonic vs Polyphonic Detections

Another division in sound event detection refers to the number of sounds present at a time for an audio clip. In monophonic environments, only one sound event is meant to occur at a time, simplifying the modeling process. However, as mentioned above, many real-world recordings contain overlapping sounds. One just needs to think of a domestic environment such as a kitchen, where is practically impossible for sound events not to overlap (cooking, speech, home appliances etc.). Polyphonic sound event detection addresses this complexity by assuming the overlap of multiple sound events temporal and frequency-wise [4]. This task is particularly important for datasets like DESED and FSD50K, which are relevant to this research and will be inspected in more detail further in this thesis.

Weakly vs Strongly Labeled Data

The availability of annotation-quality datasets tends to influence the modeling strategy chosen in each case. These annotations can be separated into weak and strong labels. Strong labels include precise timestamps for each sound event, which facilitates supervised learning for temporal localization, but their main drawback is that they are quite difficult to obtain. By contrast, weak labels only contain clip-level information regarding the present classes in each clip, a feature that makes them much easier to collect but at the same time implies a significant challenge for learning quality temporal patterns. Recent advances in Multiple instance Learning (MIL) and attention mechanisms have attempted to fill this gap [5].

2.1.2 Model architectures

The performance of SED systems is highly dependent on the model architectures they use. For the recent years, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and their recurrent extensions have become a popular approach due to their ability to learn robust audio features and representations from spectrogram inputs. This section provides a brief overview of important models used in SED, specifically focusing on the FSD-SINet model, which is crucial to the Freesound analysis pipeline.

Convolutional Neural Networks and CRNNs

CNNs form the main foundation of many SED systems by combining local time-frequency feature extraction with global feature integration. Their capacity for translation invariance enables them to detect important audio characteristics independently of slight temporal or spectral shifts [4]. To better model temporal dependencies across frames, CNNs are usually combined with Recurrent Neural Networks, resulting in Convolutional Recurrent Neural Networks (CRNNs) that can capture a better context [6]. CRNNs have demonstrated strong performance in polyphonic SED benchmarks such as DCASE challenges.

The FSD-SINet Model: Increasing Shift-Invariance

The FSD-SINet model developed by Fonseca and Serra [7] represents a notorious improvement for the Freesound analysis pipeline. It addresses imperfect shift-invariance, which is the main limitation for standard CNNs in SED. Standard convolutions can be sensitive to small shifts in the input signal, causing detection issues. However, FSD-SINet integrates Shift-Invariant Convolutions (SINets) that increase the conventional CNN layers to improve robustness to problematic shifts, stabilizing the feature extraction process. The resulting predictions for this model provide improved generalization for the weakly-labeled dataset FSD50K.

2.1.3 Evaluation metrics

Evaluating SED systems requires choosing metrics that can properly evaluate both sound event classification and the detection of the event temporal boundaries.

F1 Score

The F1 Score is still one of the most popular metrics used for SED evaluation. It represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, therefore balancing and penalizing both false positives and false negatives. The two most frequently used variants are:

- F1-Macro: This metric computes the F1 score independently for each class and averages them, so it gives the same importance to all classes regardless of their frequency in the dataset.
- Per-class F1: This metric calculates the F1 score for each class, so that strengths and weaknesses of the model are available for each category to facilitate targeting improvements.

F1-based metrics usually treat sound events as binary occurrences in fixed segments length, which may not take into account temporal localization accuracy.

Event-based metrics

Apart from segment-level metrics such as the mentioned F1 Scores, SED evaluation systems often use event-based metrics for the sake of temporal accuracy. These metrics consider time boundaries of the predicted events compared to ground truth annotations [8].

- **Event-based F1 Score and ER:** Proposed in the DCASE challenges, these metrics evaluate the accuracy of detections based on onset and offsets, handling missed, false and overlapping events.
- **Polyphonic Sound Detection Score:** This metric has been recently introduced to provide a better handling of polyphonic and overlapping events. PSDS integrates both segment-level and event-level detections offering an increase in robustness for real-world applications.

Despite PSDS providing richer evaluation results, the F1-Macro and per-class F1 still remain standard and popular choices for benchmarking and comparative analysis in many SED systems studies.

Mean Average Precision

mAP is a widely used clip-based metric in multi-label classifications and detections tasks. It measures the average precision (AP) across all classes and it is especially helpful to evaluate how well a model ranks classes over entire audio clips, which is a common practice in weakly labeled sound event detections tasks [7].

2.2 Datasets and benchmarks

2.2.1 DCASE Datasets

The development and benchmarking of Sound Event Detections systems, similarly to other related fields of study, rely on standardized datasets that can provide annotated audio for both training and evaluation. Over the past decade, the SED

community has converged around a set of datasets that contain diverse acoustic environments, scenes and events, framed within the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) challenge.

DCASE Challenge Datasets

The DCASE series, held annually since 2013, has played a fundamental role in common benchmarks for SED and other related tasks. These challenges have introduced several datasets focused on different aspects of audio scene analysis such as audio scene classification, single and multi-channel event detection and weakly supervised learning. [8]. A particularly influential subset is DCASE Task 4, which treats the polyphonic sound event detection under weakly labeled (or unlabeled) conditions being a good approach to deal with real-world situations and constraints. In the context of DCASE Task 4, the DESED (Domestic Environment Sound Event Detection) dataset has been notably important. This dataset has been developed to simulate realistic domestic acoustic environments while remaining controllable and reproducible. DESED contains real and synthetic recordings organized as seen in 1:

- The synthetic subset is generated by mixing isolated sound events diverse soundscapes. It provides strong temporal annotations, make it a really good fit for supervised learning to evaluate temporal precision.
- The real subset includes unlabeled, weakly, and strongly labeled data separated into training and validation for the development set and the public evaluation set.

This dual composition allows to test models under different learning conditions and has become a standard benchmark for evaluating models.

2.2.2 FSD50K

FSD50K is a large-scale open dataset designed for multi-label sound classification systems and audio tagging, with a strong emphasis on diversity, realism and scalability. Released in 2020 by Fonseca et al., it is extracted from the Freesound platform

Figure 1: DESED dataset composition overview

and can be used as a critical benchmark for audio classification models training with real-world sound content [2].

Dataset composition

FSD50K consists of over 51.000 audio clips extracted from Freesound. These clips are labeled using a subset of the AudioSet ontology [1], using 200 unbalanced sound classes ranging through several labels classified by sound source (human voice) or its means of production (bang), which can be hierarchically sorted according its ontology. The dataset is split into development and evaluation, with weak labels, metadata, and clips with lengths ranging from 0.3 to 30 seconds, reflecting the variability and unpredictability of real-worlds acoustic scenarios. It is important to highlight that all audio files are drawn from an open domain, and that FSD50K includes an annotator bounded tool to validate category annotations with over 600 contributors.

2.3 Post-processing of Sound Event Detection outputs

2.3.1 General techniques

Post-processing plays a crucial role in transforming raw outputs from SED models into human-readable data so that the event detections can be properly interpreted by end-users. This section reviews the most popular techniques such as thresholding and median filtering.

Thresholding

The most basic yet common method for postprocessing is probability thresholding. Given that SED models tend to output a matrix of frame-wise class probabilities, either a fixed or class-dependent threshold can be applied to determine if the confidence of a present class is enough for the sound event to be active at the given frame. This binarization of the sound event time boundaries converts the model output into a hard decision making process. While it is a straightforward technique, using a global threshold (e.g., 0.5) may underperform for unbalanced sets or when the confidence tends to vary a lot for a single class. For this reason, using class-dependent thresholding is often a reasonable approach, tuning the threshold according to validation data.

Median filtering

Another popular method for smoothing sound event detection outputs is median filtering. This approach provides a better handling of sudden isolated detections or gaps as seen in 2. Median filtering is applied to the binary predictions over time after thresholding, by using a sliding window of an odd size that typically takes from 3 to 11 frames. The kernel size of the median filter is sometimes determined empirically, depending on the expected behavior of sound classes involved in the process. In some implementations, class-dependent median filtering is used to better match the temporal behavior of the different considered classes.

Figure 2: Real (green) vs. Predicted (orange) boundaries for an audio event before (up) and after (down) median filtering.

Despite these being the two most popular approaches regarding sound event detection postprocessing there are other auxiliary steps such as minimum event duration enforcement or merging temporally adjacent events that can also result helpful.

2.3.2 Learning based post-processing

Even though conventional post-processing techniques such as thresholding and median filtering are effective for improving the predictions of SED models, sometimes they still fail to capture the huge complexity of real-world sound scenes. In order to address this limitations, recent research has explored more sophisticated post-processing methods. A notable example is the approach proposed by Giannakopoulos et al. (2022), in which Reinforcement Learning is used to optimize the post-processing pipeline of a SED model. In this context, a learning agent learns to configure parameters for the post-processing operations of thresholding and median-filtering to maximize evaluation for metrics such as F1 score or ERR [9]. More specifically, it learns to optimize per-class values for thresholds and median filtering window sizes. The agent is trained using Policy Gradient methods to find the aimed optimal configuration. This approach has shown improvements over manual tuning in experiments on DCASE datasets, highlighting the power of adaptive data-driven postprocessing. As the SED field evolves, the use of learning-based models into the

post-processing pipeline shows a promising direction for future work.

2.3.3 In the context of Freesound

In the context of the Freesound analysis pipeline, which is responsible for extracting certain properties from sounds using different analyzers and storing the results in the database, the major analyzer regarding SED is FSD-SINet [7], which is why this work focuses on its results for post-processing and later visualization. However, in this field of study we still can find other notorious analyzers and models worth to mention within the current pipeline.

- YAMNet Model: a pre-trained deep net that predicts to the 521 audio event classes in the AudioSet ontology.
- Bird-NET Analyzer, which has especially popular among the community of ornithologists due to its ability of identifying specific species of birds by their calls and songs [10].

Postprocessing for FSD-SINet analyzer

The current postprocessing pipeline for this model is quite straightforward and one of the main areas of improvement targeted by this work. A static threshold is set to a current value of 0.7 which is used to filter the resulting confidences generated by the FSD-SINet model. After this step, time boundaries are defined following the 0.5 hop-size that divides the audio clip frames. By checking both onsets and offsets for each detection, consecutive events are assembled as a single event detection if there is a match between both parameters.

As visited in the previous section, this postprocessing approach can be improved by making it class-dependent and including popular methods such as median filtering. It is important to mention that the Freesound database not only contains the resulting sound event detections from this analysis but also the raw data for the top-10 detected classes for each analyzed audio clip.

2.4 User interfaces for sound annotations

2.4.1 General visualization techniques

The visualization of sound annotations is a key aspect in audio user interfaces, facilitating user interactions with audio data or metadata over time or frequency. This section overviews some standard visualization techniques used across different domains such as music production or online sharing platforms that help users interpret and manipulate audio content.

Waveform-Centered displays

One of the most common approaches is the use of waveform plots, which provide a time-domain representation of audio and serve as visual reference for locating events based on signal level information. Platforms like **SoundCloud** use this kind of display to allow users to add comments or annotations on specific timestamps overlaying the waveform as seen in 3. These interactive markers enable intuitive alignment between annotations and audio [11].

Figure 3: Soundcloud comments displayed along time axis each at a time instant.

Spectrogram-Based displays

While waveform views are widely used in platforms or applications that target a broader, general public, spectrogram displays offer a proper insight into the frequency content of audio over time and are usually employed in more domain-specific tools. While spectrograms provide visual information on energy over time, so do

Figure 4: Different types of sound annotations generated by Sonic Visualizer, each on a different label. Note that each annotation can have an associated customizable text. Text (blue), notes (red), regions (green), boxes (purple), time instants (bright red, vertical line).

spectrograms using color coding while using the vertical axis for the frequency information display. This approach is popular and available in tools like **Sonic Visualizer** [12] and **Praat** [13], where annotations can include labels of different types, as seen in 4. More specifically, Sonic Visualizer benefits from a multiple layer customizable approach including notes, regions, boxes and text layers apart from the usual waveform and spectrograms displays.

Common patterns and methodologies

There are several visual and interaction common design patterns across annotation interfaces.

- Annotations layers: usage of stacked layers for different type of labels or annotations.
- Zoomable timelines: enabling detailed inspection for content displays.
- Region selection and editing: allowing users to define, adjust and manipulate annotation regions directly on the visualization.

- Color coding: used to distinguish format sharing annotations.

These interface patterns are the baseline upon which more specialized SED user interfaces are developed, as will be explored in the following section.

2.4.2 SED systems user interfaces

As Sound Event Detection systems are getting more integrated into real-world applications, the design of user interfaces to display their outputs has become more important. These interfaces must show not only the occurrence of events over time, but also class name and confidence.

Mobile and consumer applications

One of the most prominent real-world examples is the BirdNET app [14], a mobile application that uses the deep learning based SED system mentioned in Section 2.3.3 to identify bird species in audio recordings [10]. The app's interface displays:

- A spectrogram visualization of the user's recording.
- Overlaid time-bounded boxes for the segment of the recording the user wants to analyze.
- Individual displays for detected birds containing the species common names, scientific names and a text answer for the detection confidence e.g. *Almost certain*, given the user's location and time of the year, as seen in 5.

Although the analysis is performed on the audio segment selected by the user and consequently, the displayed results do not provide time boundaries for the event detections, the BirdNET app is definitely one of the most notorious approaches to consider regarding the display of sound event detection results.

2.4.3 Freesound interfaces and tools

The current Freesound interface for sound display varies depending on the URL context in which the sounds appear. For this project, the focus will shift to the *big*

Figure 5: Left: BirdNET App in the analysis boundaries setting step. Right: BirdNET App displaying detection results.

player format, as it is the one that will be used going forward. Other types of players include only a subset of features designed for faster and more convenient interactions (such as bookmarking or searching for similar sounds, which are placed outside the player for big displays). The player controls that provide user interactions include the following functionalities:

- Play/Pause toggle: shows a progress bar along the time axis according to the audio playing. When paused, progress bar stops at its timestamp.
- Stop button: restarts the audio progress bar to origin (00:00).
- Loop button: activates the audio loop reproduction.
- Waveform/Spectrogram toggle: changes the sound display from waveform to spectrogram as seen in 6 and 7.
- Ruler button: displays audio data when hovering over the audio clip according to the mouse pointer position. For the horizontal axis it always shows the timestamp relative to the mouse position in the player. For the vertical axis position either the dB level or the frequency are displayed depending on the display mode, waveform for the former and spectrogram for the latter.

Figure 6: Freesound display in waveform mode.

Figure 7: Freesound display in spectrogram mode.

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Postprocessing proposals

In order to improve the postprocessing for the outputs of the FSD-SINet model, this section implements two methods and proposes another one in an attempt to contribute to a better performance of the Freesound analyzer in question. Finally, an extra step is applied to improve the model display of detected classes for human readability purposes.

Note that to proceed with these methodologies, the FSD50K dataset has undergone some curation beforehand. For the sake of efficiency, instead of analyzing the audio files directly with FSD-SINet, the raw data results have been obtained from the Freesound database using the following URL format:

```
https://freesound.org/data/analysis/<SOUND\_ID//1000>/<SOUND\_ID>-fsd-sinet\_v1.json.frames.json
```

This functionality is remarkably helpful for this framework as it saves up a lot of data space and time. The resulting *.json* files provide the top 10 confidence classes per frame with a minimum confidence of 0.10. This set of files has been the baseline for the following work for the FSD50K development and evaluation subsets, which have been filtered against the available analysis files in the Freesound database.

3.1.1 Empirical observation on FSD50K dataset

Regarding the use of a static threshold for the hard decision-making process on the output probabilities, the usage of specific, per-class thresholds arises. Given the diversity in both the Freesound audio collection and the set of classes present in the FSD50K dataset, it is evident that an adaptive threshold will improve the global performance of the analyzer. For example, intuitively the singularity of a sound event labeled as *applause* requires a less strict threshold than more ambiguous labels such as *boiling* or *gurgling*. Apart from obtaining an adaptive threshold per class, the lack of a median filtering step in the post-processing raises what could be done in this aspect too. Following the previous idea, setting an specific window size per class helps out smoothing output detections, given that in the temporal domain there is also a wide range of behaviors depending on class (see *Thunder* and *Thunderstorm*).

In order to obtain adaptive parameters for both operations, a simple observational approach is proposed. It consists of taking a set of different kernel sizes and computing thresholds with different restriction parameters per class and audio clip. By postprocessing the evaluation set with each group of variables and comparing them to ground-truth annotations, the best threshold and kernel sizes can be selected for each class.

Threshold computations

To determine class-specific decision thresholds, a multi-stage computation process is employed. For each raw analysis file and corresponding class, an array of frame-level thresholds is extracted based classes marked as active in the ground truth annotations.

Once this per-frame threshold progression is obtained for a given class and audio clip, a segmentation process is applied. Within each segment, the mean and standard deviation of the activation scores are computed and combined to form a set of representative thresholds:

$$\text{frameThresholds} = \{\text{avg}(s) + \text{std}(s) \mid s \in \text{segments}\}$$

A file-level threshold is then computed by averaging these frame-level values:

$$\text{fileThreshold} = \text{avg}(\text{frameThresholds}, \text{weighted} = \text{False})$$

At this stage, both weighted and simple averages are considered by the length of the active segments. The outcome of this process is a set of N file-level thresholds for each class, where N denotes the number of analysis files available in the dataset.

To aggregate these into a single, representative threshold per class, a percentile-based reduction is applied across the N values. This enables the derivation of class-specific thresholds with varying degrees of restrictiveness.

Postprocessing subsets

At this point of the postprocessing pipeline, a total of $2P$ threshold sets are available, where P denotes the number of percentiles considered in the previous step. Each threshold is computed using both weighted and simple averaging approaches, resulting in two variants per percentile.

In order to determine the optimal combination of thresholds and median filter kernel size per class, a binary prediction matrix must be obtained for every file and threshold set. However, the raw activation outputs provided by the analysis files only contain scores for the top 10 detected classes per frame. To reconstruct the complete activation matrix, missing frame-class combinations are assigned a value of 0.

Given the reconstructed activation matrix \mathcal{A} , predictions are computed for each threshold set \mathcal{T} , kernel size $k \in \mathcal{K}$, and class $i \in \mathcal{C}$ as follows:

$$\text{filePredictions}_{s_k, T} = \text{MedianFilter}_k(\{\mathbf{1}[a_i > T_i] \mid i = 1, \dots, C, a \in \mathcal{A}\}), \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$$

This procedure results in $2PK$ prediction sets per file. In the current configuration, the set of kernel sizes is defined as $K = [1, 3, 5, 7]$ and percentiles considered are $P = [50, 60, 70, 80]$ resulting in 32 different postprocessing configurations.

Finally, for each class, the combination of threshold and kernel size that maximizes the F1-score on validation data is selected and recorded in the final postprocessing set.

3.1.2 Tag recommendation methods applied to SED techniques

Sound Event Detection (SED) systems operate across a wide variety of sounds, each characterized by different levels of polyphony, ambient conditions and recording equipment. Given this diversity, the per-class parameter selection methods described in the previous section may lack scalability and generalizability, especially when applied to large-scale, heterogeneous audio collections such as Freesound.

To address this limitation, it becomes important to think of adaptive strategies that do not rely on other sounds statistical observations. Since the ground truth annotations provide only weak labels, the SED task can, in this context, be approached similarly to an audio tagging problem.

In this field of study, the tag selection methods for recommendation purposes proposed by Font, 2015 [15] are a solid baseline. Among these, the most effective method described in Section 3.2.3 ("Selection of tags to recommend") is the *percentage strategy*, which involves selecting tags whose scores surpass a fixed percentage of the highest tag score.

Exporting this approach to the current SED task introduces certain considerations. In fact, this tag recommendation method is designed to always output at least one tag, and this assumption does not hold in SED, where many frames can contain no active sound events. Therefore, a class is only considered active at a given frame if its confidence score surpasses both a static threshold (e.g., 0.45) and at least 80% of the highest confidence score observed among all classes for that frame.

$$\text{ActiveClass}(c, t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a_{c,t} > \tau_{\min} \text{ and } a_{c,t} > \alpha \cdot \max_{j \in \mathcal{C}} a_{j,t} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where $a_{c,t}$ is the activation score for class c at frame t , τ_{\min} is a fixed minimum threshold (0.45), α is the relative threshold parameter (0.8), and \mathcal{C} is the set of all classes.

3.1.3 Hierarchy filtering for human-readable results

The current output format of the FSD-SINet model is structured as a dictionary containing the following elements:

- A list of dictionaries with event detection information, including class name, time boundaries, and confidence score.
- A list of all unique classes detected within the audio file.
- A list of embeddings resulting from the audio analysis.

While this structure provides the essential data needed to build a visualization system for Freesound users, two important considerations must be addressed to improve the human readability and interpretability of the output.

On the one hand, it is important to acknowledge that the vocabulary used by the FSD50K dataset is derived from a subset of the AudioSet Ontology, which introduces a valuable but currently overlooked detail: class hierarchy. Extracting the hierarchical level for each class can significantly help organize the presentation of sound events during the visualization stage for a more intuitive and informative user experience. Note that, as the ground truth vocabulary does not include some 0-level classes (e.g. *Sounds of things* all its child classes levels will be pushed up).

On the other hand, the current system seeks an integrated display of SED data within the sound players in the Freesound platform, which poses certain limitations

in screen space. To meet this requirement, avoiding redundancy in the information display is crucial. Therefore, when multiple classes that share same time boundaries within a difference of 1 frame (0.5 seconds) are found to have a parent-child relationship in the ontology, they are merged into a single one. In such cases, the child class is selected for display because it provides more specificity for the detected sound event, as seen in 8 and 9. The code with the postprocessing and filtering of FSD-SINet results implementations can be found in appendix A.

Figure 8: Draft display for raw detections given by the FSD-SINet model current postprocessing.

Figure 9: Draft display for hierarchically filtered detections.

3.1.4 Future optimization proposals

Upon reviewing the previously discussed postprocessing strategies, it becomes straightforward that none of the presented implementations incorporate strong optimization techniques or learning-based approaches to refine postprocessing parameters with the goal of improving evaluation metrics. This highlights a methodological gap considering that optimization-driven methods are more aligned with current research trends in sound event detection.

As seen in section 2.3.2, the reinforcement learning (RL) approach proposed by Giannakopoulos et al.(2022)[9] introduces a framework capable of optimizing the entire postprocessing pipeline of a SED model such as FSD-SINet. While promising, this approach presents several challenges that must be addressed. The most notable one is the requirement for strongly labeled annotations, something the FSD50K dataset does not provide.

Nevertheless, as mentioned in section 2.2.1, the DESED dataset includes a subset of recordings with strong labels. Although these annotations are limited to domestic sound environments, several of the classes can be mapped to the FSD50K taxonomy. This opens the possibility of training the RL-based optimization system on the strongly labeled DESED subset and exporting the resulting parameters to the corresponding class subset in FSD50K. A proposal for mapping both subsets can be found below, in table 1. Note that the match between classes is challenging due to the presence of ambiguity in resolving specific classes from one set to the other.

Table 1: Mapping between DESED classes and FSD50K classes

DESED Class	FSD-SINet Class
Speech (0)	Child_speech_and_kid_speaking (33) Female_speech_and_woman_speaking (75) Male_speech_and_man_speaking (111)

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

DESED_CLASS	FSD_SINET_CLASS
	Speech (158) Human_voice (101) Chatter (29) Conversation (43)
Dog (1)	Dog (59) Bark (7) Domestic_animals_and_pets (60)
Cat (2)	Domestic_animals_and_pets (60) Cat (28) Meow (116)
Alarm/bell/ringing (3)	Alarm (4) Bell (11) Ringtone (140) Bicycle_bell (13) Church_bell (38) Cowbell (45) Doorbell (63)
Dishes (4)	Dishes_and_pots_and_pans (58)
Frying (5)	Frying_(food) (83)
Blender (6)	Domestic_sounds_and_home_sounds (61)
Running water (7)	Water (187) Water_tap_and_faucet (188) Bathtub_(filling_or_washing) (10) Fill_(with_liquid) (76) Sink_(filling_or_washing) (151) Toilet_flush (175)
Vacuum cleaner (8)	Domestic_sounds_and_home_sounds (61)

Continued on next page

Table 1 – continued from previous page

DESED_CLASS	FSD_SINET_CLASS
Electric shaver/toothbrush (9)	Domestic_sounds_and_home_sounds (61)

3.2 Visualization of SED in Freesound

This section presents all procedures regarding the development and implementation of sound event detection displays in Freesound, from general considerations to take into account for all upcoming paradigms, to presenting draft visualizations and implementing the best candidates, and finally designing how the user satisfaction evaluation will be performed.

3.2.1 General considerations

This subsection outlines the development and implementation process for displaying sound event detection (SED) results from the FSD-SINet model within the Freesound platform. It begins with general considerations that apply across all subsequent visualization paradigms, followed by the presentation of draft display proposals, the implementation of selected candidates, and the definition of the methodology to evaluate user satisfaction.

Data features

The visualization of FSD-SINet results for a given audio clip will include the following elements:

- The class name of the detected event.
- The time boundaries indicating the temporal location of the event.
- The confidence score associated with the detection.
- The hierarchical level of the class within the ontology.

These features can be grouped based on their relevance for the user interface. On the one hand, class names and time boundaries carry the most critical information and should therefore be prioritized in any visualization approach. On the other hand, the confidence score and hierarchy level, while not crucial, can improve user understanding and interpretation of the detection results. Note that a common property across all displays is that color coding is used for class identification, accompanied by a legend appended below the player container. The chosen set of colors is selected to avoid interference with Freesound default waveform display colors.

As a result, the specific format and encoding of the information may vary between different visualization proposals, with each one presenting these parameters using different visual strategies depending on its intended use and emphasis.

Finally, it is important to mention that the displayed results correspond to the current postprocessing pipeline for the FSD-SINet model, adding the ontology filter process described in Section 3.1.3

User interaction

Similarly to the data features described above, the proposed visualization paradigms also share a set of common user interaction functionalities. These shared properties are designed to ensure intuitive and efficient interaction with detected events.

- **Mouse click interaction:** Clicking on a displayed sound event will automatically move the progress bar to the event's start time and begin playback from that point. This feature is designed to facilitate user evaluation and to enable quick verification of detected events.
- **Mouse hover functionality:** when hovering over a visualized event, a label will appear showing key details such as the event's class name, confidence score and time boundaries. This ensures that users can access detailed information without cluttering the main interface.
- **Overlay display behavior:** By default, SED visualizations will not be shown for analyzed sounds. Instead, a toggle button integrated into the audio player's

control bar will allow users to show or hide a visual overlay containing the detections information. This layered approach aims to maintain a clean interface while still providing access to the analysis results.

These interaction features are particularly relevant given that the proposed visualizations vary in the amount of information displayed by default. Also, they have been designed for enabling user experience with the results in a meaningful and non-intrusive manner.

3.2.2 Visualization drafts

This section introduces a series of visualization drafts each offering a distinct approach to presenting sound event detection results. Every proposal is outlined with its key strengths and potential limitations to provide a comprehensive comparison and later choose the best candidates.

VisualiSED 01: Class-wise distributed rectangles

This approach arranges labels along different vertical levels, each corresponding to a separate sound class. Class names are displayed at the start of the player container in their corresponding level, while individual event detections are represented as rectangles extending over their time intervals as seen in 10. Each rectangle includes a text of the confidence score expressed as a percentage. Whenever space is insufficient for the confidence display due to short sound events, this information is still accessible through mouse hover interaction. A significant strength of this design is its effective handling of overlapping events, which tends to be a challenging task in the visualization of SED outputs. By grouping events by class and allocating each to a different vertical track, overlapping is avoided. However, this approach can have some trouble with sounds containing a high number of distinct classes.

VisualiSED 02: Level-wise distributed rectangles

To address the space limitations identified in the previous proposal, this method retains the same basic structure (representing events as rectangles indicating their time

Figure 10: Draft display for VisualSED 01

boundaries), but introduces a hierarchical organization of classes 11. Event classes are grouped and displayed according to their hierarchy level, based on the filtered ontology discussed in 3.1.3. This modification ensures that visualization remains limited to a maximum of four vertical levels, resolving the space issue described in *VisualiSED 01*.

Figure 11: Draft display for VisualiSED 02

However, the primary limitation of this approach is its ability to handle overlapping events that belong to the same hierarchy level. Bearing in mind that many classes have a reduced level due to ontology filtering, these troublesome cases are more likely and frequent than the problematic ones reported in *VisualiSED 01*.

VisualiSED 03: Nested hierarchy rectangles

In an attempt to establish a compromise between the two previously described approaches, this method combines the advantages of class-wise organization with the structure of class hierarchies. In this design, each detected top-level class is assigned a distinct vertical level, similar to the first proposal, while hierarchical relationships are encoded through nested rectangles. These rectangles are color-coded by class as usual, which helps maintain clarity.

Figure 12: Draft display for VisualiSED 03

Although this design effectively uses both class distinction and hierarchy, it introduces challenges such as potential overlaps between child events of shared parent classes. Furthermore, it strongly depends on precise time boundaries, as issues can arise, for example, when the boundaries of a child event exceed their parents. Finally, the vast majority of Freesound users might not be familiar with the **AudioSet Ontology** hierarchical organization, which devalues this method.

VisualiSED 04: Sonic region display

In order to reduce visual clutter in the player interface, this approach builds upon the same structure as *VisualiSED 01*, but replaces the rectangular representations with a more minimalistic layout inspired by the *region layer* annotations found in **Sonic Visualizer** [12], as seen in 13. In this design, each detected event is represented by a single horizontal line with vertical ticks marking its time boundaries.

Figure 13: Draft display for VisualiSED 04

This method offers a cleaner and more compact visualization, useful when dealing with a high number of detections or events density. However, it loses some clarity in terms of confidence identification, which is less immediately visible compared to other proposals. Additionally, the fact that it lacks a filled visual area can reduce the precision of short detections.

VisualiSED 05: Onset detections

To provide a different perspective on this task and to move away from the layout strategies used in previous proposals, this approach uses an onset-based representation as seen in Figure 14. The interface remains minimal and uncluttered by displaying events only as vertical lines positioned at their onset times, with class confidence encoded using different line styles as follows:

$$\text{LineStyle}(c) = \begin{cases} \textit{solid} & \text{if } c \geq 0.8 \\ \textit{dashed} & \text{else if } 0.6 \leq c < 0.8 \\ \textit{dotted} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This simple design is the least visually intrusive of all, making it suitable for real-time applications. However, this is not the application's case, and it comes with notable limitations: key information such as class identity and event duration is not

Figure 14: Draft display for VisualiSED 05

directly visible, and the method is highly dependent on accurate onset detection for a good interpretation.

VisualiSED 06: Detailed Onsets

To address the lack of crucial information mentioned in *VisualiSED 05*, this method presents a very similar layout that incorporates class name, confidence score, and duration for each detected event. The visualization format consists of a rising vertical line at the event onset, followed by a horizontal segment extending until the event's offset, and finishing with a descending line to form a semi-rectangular shape. Above the horizontal segment, the class name and confidence score are displayed.

To manage overlapping detections, the height of each new overlapped segment is slightly reduced, allowing detections to be stacked without interfering with one another. This strategy successfully maintains a compact and informative design while enabling the display of key event parameters. Nevertheless, this design may encounter some issues when dealing with multiple short-duration events, which can affect the readability of text labels.

3.2.3 Best user interfaces

This subsection outlines the final set of visualization designs selected for implementation and subsequent user satisfaction evaluation. For each chosen approach, the

Figure 15: Draft display for VisualiSED 06

underlying rationale is briefly discussed, along with minor adjustments introduced to enhance human readability. The source code for these implementations is available on GitHub ¹, which can also be accessed through appendix A

VisualiSED 01: Class-wise Levels

This design handles overlapping events very effectively by assigning each class its own level, ensuring the most clean and readable layout. Although it may struggle with limited vertical space, it offers the clearest representation of time and class. Given the prioritization of clarity and separation, it is expected to be widely accepted by the broad community of Freesound users.

For the implementation process, some considerations need to be taken into account. To avoid a cluttered interface but preserving a comfortable visualization of detected sound events, rectangles opacity will follow this rule according to the display mode of the sound:

$$\text{Opacity}(c) = \begin{cases} 0.8 & \text{if } \text{displayMode} = \text{Waveform} \\ 1 & \text{else if } \text{displayMode} = \text{Spectrogram} \end{cases}$$

Similarly, borders styling will behave as follows:

¹<https://github.com/MTG/freesound/tree/visualize-sed>

$$\text{BorderStyle}(c) = \begin{cases} 3\text{px} - \text{Solid} & \text{if } c \geq 0.9 \\ 2\text{px} - \text{Solid} & \text{else if } 0.8 \leq c < 0.9 \\ 1\text{px} - \text{Dashed} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

VisualiSED 06: Detailed Onsets

This approach retains the minimal nature of onset-based visuals, but overcomes its limitations by including crucial data in SED systems. The added structural logic for overlapping events is a practical solution that preserves readability under all circumstances. This design prioritizes compactness alongside rich information, which makes it a really strong candidate for good results on user satisfaction.

VisualiSED 02: Hierarchy Levels

This method manages vertical space efficiently organizing events by ontology levels, especially in diverse sound scenes. While it may face overlap issues within the same level, this design is more scalable than the class-wise approach and leverages semantic grouping, which enhances using comprehension. The use of semantic organization is not expected to report as good results as the previously selected designs, but it is still interesting to observe how user satisfaction develops in this case.

Regarding the conditional format for rectangles, in this implementation the same rules as in *VisualiSED 01* are followed.

3.3 User satisfaction experiment design

This section presents the design of the user satisfaction experiment. The chosen files to be tested and questions for the user's survey are presented as well as data collection methods.

3.3.1 Dataset Files

The sounds selected for the final user satisfaction experiment are chosen based on a set of criteria to ensure a representative range of SED behaviors while keeping the experiment efficient.

- Dataset size must be kept small (10-20 sounds) in order to make the experiment agile enough.
- It must contain a representative sample of various classes present in the FSD50K dataset.
- It must contain diverse files in terms of event density and variety (from field recordings to single event audio clips).
- Recordings must not be longer than 30 seconds for the analysis to be run without skipping.

Based on these considerations, the following sound IDs have been selected from the Freesound development database: 463464, 75825, 347223, 217543, 685989, 682534, 436790, 49520, 671901, 181628, 437623, 463472. For more information of its type of content see the following 2, with classified sounds according to the AudioSet Ontology parent class and the amount of sources present in sound (single vs multiple).

Table 2: Experiment dataset

ID	Source	Human	Animals	Music	Ambiguous	Things	Natural
463464	Multiple	True	False	False	False	False	False
347223	Multiple	True	False	False	False	False	False
217543	Multiple	False	False	True	False	False	False
685989	Multiple	False	False	False	False	True	False
682534	Single	False	True	False	False	False	False

Continued on next page

Table 2 – continued from previous page

ID	Source	Human	Animals	Music	Ambiguous	Things	Natural
436790	Multiple	False	False	False	False	False	True
49520	Multiple	True	True	False	False	False	False
671901	Single	False	False	True	False	False	False
181628	Multiple	False	False	False	True	True	False
463472	Multiple	True	False	True	False	False	False
437623	Multiple	True	False	False	True	True	False
75825	Multiple	False	False	False	False	True	True

3.3.2 Experiment design

To assess user satisfaction with the selected SED visualization designs, an online mock experiment has been conducted using Google Forms. The form presents participants with previously outlined set of analyzed Freesound sound URLs, containing visualizations generated using the final set of display designs described in the previous section.

The main objective of the experiment is to obtain a general assessment and evaluate the clarity, usability, and perceived usefulness of each visualization approach as well as the quality of the generated detections. Participants will be asked to listen to each audio clip while observing the corresponding visual representations and then answer a series of short questions to capture their impressions.

The final questionnaire is short and concise to encourage participation. For each visualization design, there is one question addressing the quality of the event annotations while the remaining focus on the effectiveness of the visual design: helpfulness, layout clarity, considering hypothetical usefulness when exploring sounds in Freesound and an optional comment box for any suggestions etc. The 4 sounds visited for each visualization display are randomly selected. The responses have been collected using a 0 – 10 grading scale and a 5-point Likert scale ranging from *Strongly agree* to *Strongly disagree* as follows.

1. How would you rate the accuracy and quality of the event annotations in this visualization? *0-10 grade scale.*
2. The visualization helped me understand the events present in the audio clip. *5-point Likert scale.*
3. The layout and visual organization of the events were clear and easy to interpret. *5-point Likert scale.*
4. I think this visualization would be useful when exploring sounds in Freesound. *5-point Likert scale.*
5. Optional: Any suggestions or observations about this visualization? *Text answer.*

Additionally, at the end of the survey, there is an optional box to leave any message or observations the user wishes to provide.

Due to the impact that the proposed changes could have on Freesound, both in terms of visualization displays and the integration of the modifications in the FSD-SINet analyzer, the experiment has not yet been distributed to the wider Freesound community. Instead, it has been carried out with a smaller group of participants close to me, including specialists in audio and UX design as well as individuals without prior knowledge of the field.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Postprocessing approaches

The current postprocessing strategy for the FSD-SINet model relies on a fixed threshold of 0.7, which is applied to retain only the most confident detections. In this work, two alternative approaches have been explored: (i) class-dependent thresholds and kernel sizes determined through empirical observation, and (ii) the use of tag-recommendation techniques adapted to sound event detection.

For the evaluation of these approaches, the input consisted of the raw outputs of the FSD-SINet model, namely the top-10 frame-wise class confidences for the FSD50K evaluation set. Performance was measured by computing the F-Score for each methodology, with the resulting values summarized in Table 3.

In the first method, based on empirical observation, parameters were estimated using the development set. For each class, this process produced a specific percentile, a kernel size, and an indication of whether the averaging should account for detection length. Analysis of these results showed that the most common configuration corresponded to the 50th percentile with kernel size $k = 1$, without length-weighted averaging. However, this choice of parameters is also the least intrusive, making the approach closely resemble the baseline and therefore reducing its potential impact.

Considering the F-Score of each postprocessing approach, for the final user experiment the used postprocessing is the current static threshold combined with the hierarchy filtering described in section 3.1.3.

Figure 16: Distributions for percentiles P and kernel size values K parameters.

Table 3: Comparison of approaches and their performance

Approach	Useful parameters	Macro F1
Per-class threshold and kernel size	Percentiles = [50, 60, 70, 80] Kernel sizes = [1, 3, 5, 7]	0.3385
Tag recommendation percentual approach	Min. threshold = 0.45 Valid percentage = 0.8	0.344
Current static threshold	Threshold = 0.7	0.3869

4.2 Qualitative insights on detections

Given the ultimate goal of this work to evaluate the real-world user experience, it is important to provide insight into how the hierarchy filtering step described in 3.1.3 affects both the display and specificity of detections. The full collection of images can be found in the appendix B, though the most notable effects are illustrated in 17.

It is clear that the filtering process not only removes some general detections but also organizes the remaining ones according to a hierarchy, displaying parent-child relationships from top to bottom.

While the aim of this feature is to improve specificity and enhance usability for the end user, it can sometimes lead to less accurate displays. In particular, a parent class with more accurately defined time boundaries may be omitted in favor of more specific, but less precise, child classes. This effect is illustrated in 17, where the broader *Bird* class better matches the full duration of the bird singing than the more specific *Bird vocalization and bird call and bird song* class.

4.3 User Satisfaction Survey Results

This section presents the results of the user satisfaction survey, which evaluated both the underlying detection quality of the FSD-SINet model and the effectiveness of three different visualization designs for displaying these detections. A total of 12 participants completed the survey. Each participant listened to four sounds per visualization, randomly selected from the set of 12 sounds, ensuring all sounds were evaluated while introducing variation in the sequence. The questionnaire structure is previously defined in section 3.3.2. The results are presented in groups by evaluation topic and all the materials related to the survey can be found in appendix A.

4.3.1 Annotation accuracy

Given that all visualization designs rely on the same underlying detections, this assessment directly reflects user confidence in the model outputs. The distribution of responses (Figure 18) shows a central tendency around the middle of the scale (Mean = 4.31), which indicates only moderate perceived accuracy, with noticeable variability (SD = 1.34) and a wide range of opinions. While some users considered the event annotations reasonably accurate, others found them less convincing, suggesting that events were sometimes missed or imprecisely localized. These evaluations highlight the need for further refinement in detection performance and postprocessing approaches to improve user interpretability of SED outputs.

In parallel to the survey, a small manually annotated dataset was prepared for the twelve sounds included in the experiment that can be found in appendix A. These annotations provide a reference for assessing the alignment between the FSD-

SINet detections and the actual acoustic events. Although a detailed quantitative comparison was outside the scope of this work, preliminary observations suggest that discrepancies between manual annotations and model outputs explain the lower user ratings. This dataset can therefore serve as a valuable baseline for future validation and improvement efforts.

4.3.2 Visualization effectiveness

The results of the questions referring to the performance of the different visualization designs reveal differences in how participants perceive the quality of the three displays. Regarding the question of whether the visualization helped users understand the events present in the audio clip (Q2), the Class-Wise design (VS01) received the strongest positive feedback, with 11 participants agreeing and 1 strongly agreeing, and no negative responses. The Detailed Onsets design (VS06) was also positively received, with 8 agreeing and 3 strongly agreeing, though one participant expressed neutrality. The Level-Wise design (VS02) showed more mixed results, with 5 participants agreeing, 3 neutral, and 4 disagreeing, suggesting some users found it less intuitive for interpreting event sequences. Results can be checked in figure 19

A similar pattern emerges for layout clarity and ease of interpretation (Q3), see figure 20. The Class-Wise design again scored highly, with 8 agreeing and 3 strongly agreeing, whereas the Detailed Onsets design had 8 strongly agree responses but fewer agreeing responses overall. The Level-Wise design had more dispersed ratings, including one disagreement and two neutral responses, indicating that hierarchical grouping of events introduces some ambiguity in visual organization.

For perceived usefulness when exploring sounds in Freesound (Q4), both the Class-Wise and Detailed Onsets designs were consistently rated as useful, with 8 or more participants selecting agree or strongly agree. The Level-Wise design received more varied responses, with some participants neutral or disagreeing, reinforcing the observation that while hierarchical grouping may provide structure, it might reduce interpretability and perceived usefulness in practical exploration of sound events (see figure 21). Overall, these results suggest that the Class-Wise and Detailed On-

sets designs were generally preferred by users, offering clearer and more actionable visualizations for understanding sound events.

4.3.3 Qualitative Feedback

Summarizing the user’s feedback across the three visualization designs, participants generally highlight issues with the quality and accuracy of the detections. Many of them were missing, temporally misaligned, or overly general (e.g., “Musical instrument” for orchestral passages, “Domestic animals” instead of “Dog,” “Human group action” instead of “Applause”). Long events were often truncated, while background sounds such as footsteps or wind were undetected. Several users emphasized that the weak detection quality made it difficult to evaluate the visualizations themselves.

VisualiSED 02: Hierarchy Level-Wise Display

Users appreciated the use of confidence-dependent borders, but found overlapping rectangles confusing and visually cluttered. Labels missing event names (relying only on colors, with names displayed only on the legend) were seen as problematic for accessibility. Additionally, some users reported that the display of the labels on top of the waveform is confusing, and proposed a separate whole display similar to the toggle between waveform and spectrogram displays.

VisualiSED 06: Detailed Onsets Display

This design was generally better received. The stacking of overlapping events was considered a clear improvement, making the display less intrusive. However, temporal inconsistencies remained a major issue, particularly for applause and other continuous sounds. Some users criticized redundancy in displaying similar labels (e.g., “Motor Vehicle” multiple times). While still affected by generalistic detections, this display was often described as the most comfortable to use.

VisualiSED 01: Class-Wise Display

Several users preferred this design because of clearer alignment between detection names and their position (labels listed on the left). However, clutter remained a concern, particularly when many events were present. The overlapping of waveform and labels again drew criticism. Despite persistent detection issues, some considered this an improved version of Design A.

General Feedback

Overall, users saw potential in the visualizations but stressed that the system is not yet ready for Freesound integration. Suggestions included: separating waveforms from labels to improve readability and allowing toggling of detections via the legend to address color-blind accessibility. While detection quality was the main limitation, participants agreed that visualization could become a useful feature, especially for browsing longer audio files where it could save listening time.

Figure 17: Top: Sound 682534 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 682534 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Q1: How would you rate the accuracy and quality of the event annotations in this visualization?

Figure 18: User answers regarding quality and accuracy of detections. Mean score = 4.31, StdDev = 1.34, Range = 6.

Q2: The visualization helped me understand the events present in the audio clip.

Figure 19: User answers regarding helpfulness of the display.

Q3: The layout and visual organization of the events were clear and easy to interpret.

Figure 20: User answers regarding clarity of the display.

Q4: I think this visualization would be useful when exploring sounds in Freesound.

Figure 21: User answers regarding usefulness of the display.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Postprocessing insights

The exploration of postprocessing strategies highlights both the limitations of the current static thresholding approach and the challenges of introducing alternatives that significantly improve detection quality. Although class-dependent thresholds and kernel sizes attempt to provide a more flexible framework, the most frequently selected parameters turned out to be the least intrusive, essentially replicating the baseline behavior. The fact that this method does not capture nor low- or high-level features from sound concludes that methods driven by empirical observation do not bring substantial gains in performance. Instead, state-of-the-art approaches that are optimization-driven or learning-based appear as necessary to achieve more meaningful improvements, aligning with current research trends in sound event detection.

In parallel, the qualitative insights gained from hierarchy filtering reveal an interesting trade-off between specificity and temporal accuracy. On the one hand, filtering enhances the clarity of visualizations by structuring detections in parent–child hierarchies, which can improve interpretability for end users. On the other hand, the suppression of broader, temporally accurate parent categories in favor of narrower but less reliable child classes raises concerns about the consistency of the displayed results. This tension underscores the need for more adaptive post-processing meth-

ods that balance hierarchical specificity with annotation reliability, ensuring that end users are not confused by overly granular but inaccurate event labels.

5.2 Visualization Considerations

The evaluation of the visualization paradigms reveals that user preferences are not evenly distributed. The consistently strong performance of the Class-Wise display suggests that grouping detections by class provides a simple yet effective structure that helps users grasp the overall composition of sound events. Similarly, the Detailed Onsets design was positively received, indicating that providing finer temporal information without overcomplicating the layout can enhance users' understanding of event sequences. By contrast, the Level-Wise design received mixed evaluations, with several participants reporting difficulties in interpretation, so while hierarchical organization may align with theoretical taxonomies, it does not translate into intuitive or user-friendly visualizations in practice. Altogether, these findings highlight an important balance between detail and usability in the design of SED visualizations.

5.3 Future work

In addition to the optimization steps outlined in Section 3.1.4 related to the proposed mapping between the DESED and FSD50K datasets for postprocessing improvements, further work is required to integrate this feature into Freesound. A key step is to conduct a broader survey with the Freesound community in order to gather feedback from the actual end users of the tool. For this purpose, the evaluation form designed in this work will be revised and adapted according to the following considerations:

1. Selection of visualization designs. Based on the results obtained with the provisional form, the Hierarchy Level-Wise approach will be discarded, thereby keeping the survey shorter and more focused to encourage participation.

2. Incorporation of respondent feedback. On the one hand, suggestions such as enabling toggling between waveform/spectrogram and detections will be considered for the Class-Wise display, as its current implementation has been reported as cluttered. The Detailed Onset display, on the other hand, did not raise significant concerns and could coexist with the default Freesound displays. However, improvements to the detections legend are required, particularly in terms of color-coding and the possibility of toggling visibility per class, which would also support accessibility for color-blind users.
3. Expansion of survey dataset. Running the survey directly within the real Freesound database, rather than the local development environment used in this work, will make a broader set of sounds available. This will allow for the inclusion of additional examples to enrich the survey in future iterations.
4. Technical integration. The implementation code still requires formal review to ensure compatibility with the current Freesound workflow. An important step in this direction will be to integrate the postprocessing methodologies such as filtering and sorting directly within Freesound rather than modifying the FSD-SINet analyzer, provided this does not compromise functionality or performance of the platform.

5.4 Conclusions

This work has explored the design and evaluation of postprocessing approaches and visualization paradigms for sound event detection (SED) with the aim of enhancing user experience in Freesound. On the methodological side, the study proposed alternative postprocessing strategies to the fixed-threshold baseline of FSD-SINet, introducing class-dependent thresholds and hierarchy filtering. While these approaches showed potential to refine detections and improve interpretability, results also highlighted the limitations of empirical tuning and the trade-offs introduced by hierarchical filtering, particularly when specificity came at the expense of accuracy. These findings emphasize both the promise and the current constraints

of non-learning-based postprocessing, pointing towards reinforcement learning or optimization-driven methods as natural next steps.

On the visualization side, the user survey provided valuable insights into how different display paradigms shape interpretability. The Class-Wise and Detailed Onsets designs consistently outperformed the Level-Wise approach, being perceived as clearer, more actionable, and more useful in real-world exploration tasks. At the same time, user feedback revealed practical issues such as visual clutter, the need for toggling mechanisms, and accessibility concerns, which serve as concrete directions for improving integration into Freesound.

Overall, the thesis demonstrates the potential of combining algorithmic post-processing with thoughtful visualization design to bridge the gap between raw SED outputs and meaningful user interaction. Its main strengths lie in providing practical design insights, using a first evaluation of visualization alternatives, and identifying a clear path for integration into Freesound. However, the scope of the study was limited by the scale of the user survey and the absence of large-scale optimization-based post-processing. These weaknesses underline the need for broader evaluations datasets and methodological innovation. Nevertheless, the contributions of this work set a solid foundation for both technical refinement and user-centered development, supporting future steps toward making sound event detection more accessible and useful in everyday Freesound audio exploration.

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Appendix A

Resources and Code availability

Freesound repository branch containing the main code of the project regarding visualizations and UI/UX.

Freesound audio analyzers repository branch containing the code for the post-processing and filtering of the outputs of the FSD-SINet model.

Dataset useful information and manual annotations in Google Sheets format.

User experiment form in Google Forms format.

User experiment results collected in a Google Sheets document.

Appendix B

Filtering results

Figure 22: Top: Sound 49520 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 49520 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 23: Top: Sound 75825 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 75825 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 24: Top: Sound 181628 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 181628 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 25: Top: Sound 217543 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 217543 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 26: Top: Sound 347223 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 347223 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 27: Top: Sound 436790 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 436790 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 28: Top: Sound 437623 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 437623 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 29: Top: Sound 463464 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 463464 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 30: Top: Sound 463472 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 463472 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 31: Top: Sound 671901 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 671901 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 32: Top: Sound 685989 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 685989 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3

Figure 33: Top: Sound 685989 detections before filtering. Bottom: Sound 685989 filtered detections. Both displays following the visualization technique described in 3.2.3